

Identification of Green Corridors as a type of Urban Green Spaces.

Irada Ismayilova ^{*1} and Sabine Timpf ^{†1}

¹Institute of Geography, Geoinformatics Group, University of Augsburg, Germany

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Summary

Green corridors, despite their significance in urban environments, are rarely mapped as a distinct types of urban green spaces. Therefore, we map them using their few, but sufficiently descriptive characteristics. The proposed method integrates a height thresholding technique to identify trees and spatially associates the result with nearby linear structures such as roads and rivers. Our findings enable us to classify linear segments based on their likelihood of being green corridors, ranging from low to very high probability. Nonetheless, we emphasize the critical role of the data sets used, as a key factor in refining the accuracy of our results.

KEYWORDS: urban green spaces, green corridors, mapping green spaces, thresholding, tree extraction

1 Motivation

The development and identification of urban green spaces (UGSs) are vital for enhancing residents' quality of life and promoting environmental sustainability (Lin et al., 2019). Design of UGSs, crucial in transforming bustling cities into habitable environments for humans and wildlife, involves selecting various types of UGS and ensuring their interconnectivity. While common UGS types such as parks and forests are often isolated, optimally, they should be interconnected using linear green spaces to foster environmental benefits such as nature conservation, biodiversity, and urban climate improvement (Heidt and Neef, 2008). Furthermore, from the rewilding perspective, restoring connectivity between core areas can positively affect movement and migration across the larger landscape and help to withstand unfavorable effects of climate change (Carver et al., 2021). In this context, green corridors are of particular importance.

These corridors serve multiple environmental functions, acting as wildlife pathways, pollutant barriers, and noise pollution reducers as well as enhancing human well-being (Heidt and Neef, 2008; Lacasta et al., 2018). They also strengthen community resilience by fostering connections between people and places (Forde et al., 2023).

Although the significance of green corridors is clear, a universal definition for this term does not

*irada.ismayilova@geo.uni-augsburg.de

†sabine.timpf@geo.uni-augsburg.de

exist. Typically, they are conceived of as linear green structures linking larger, fragmented green areas in urban centers (Zhang et al., 2019; Heidt and Neef, 2008; Peng et al., 2017). Their identification is challenging due to their size, as sometimes they can appear as a thin stripe of trees. The scale of individual trees is often much smaller than the mapping unit used in most land use and land cover (LULC) maps. Thus, they never appear as a separate category or even as a subcategory of UGSs. Mapping UGSs and trees using high-resolution satellite imagery and advanced techniques such as machine learning and canopy height models is becoming more prevalent (Degerickx et al., 2020; Leichtle et al., 2021). In this research, our objective is to pinpoint linear structures along roads and rivers that may serve as green corridors. To achieve this, we utilize height thresholds to identify trees, then spatially associate them with roads and rivers, and subsequently measure their proximity to parks and forests. This approach aims to determine if linear structures with a high likelihood of being green corridors actually connect larger green spaces.

2 Case Study

To map urban corridors in our study area, we initially establish a definition of urban corridors based on semantic characteristics that will be used for their identification. We characterize urban corridors as regions marked by a linear arrangement of trees aligned with linear land features such as rivers and roads. For classification as an urban corridor, this arrangement should be consistent on both sides of these features, forming a secure passage beneficial for human and animal movement.

We test the feasibility of the proposed method in the City of Augsburg, Germany. Spanning an area of approximately 146 km², Augsburg hosts a notable number of vegetation types, including urban forest, large parks as well as smaller green spaces such as gardening areas and others. Green corridors appear mainly alongside the two main rivers, Lech and Wertach, providing tranquil areas for residents to relax, especially in the summer.

2.1 Data and Modelling

To extract tree crowns, we calculate the height of structures above the ground using an openly accessible digital elevation model (DEM) alongside a digital surface model (DSM). Typically, the height of objects above ground is depicted using a normalized digital surface model (nDSM), a derived elevation product obtained by subtracting the DEM from the DSM. We acquire both the DEM and DSM data sets from the State Office for Digitization, Broadband, and Surveying's web page, available [here](#). The DEM, offered as a free raster data set, has a spatial resolution of 1 meter, whereas the DSM, providing a finer resolution of 40 cm, is not freely available and must be purchased. The DSM data set was collected between the 9th and 19th of February 2022. To align the spatial resolution of these data sets, we resample the DEM to 40 cm and then compute the nDSM using the raster calculator tool in ArcGIS Pro version 3.1.1.

To establish accurate height thresholds for tree extraction, we manually collect approximately 100 sample training points from tree crowns using a digital orthophoto as a basis. We then calculate descriptive statistics for these sample trees.

Additionally, we utilize road and river data sets from actual land use data (Tatsächliche Nutzung) and park and forest data from the OpenStreetMap data set.

To extract green corridors, we propose a two-step identification approach. Our primary goal in the first step is to identify tree crowns by analyzing their height distribution using the nDSM data set. For each sample point, we extract height data from the nDSM and calculate various descriptive statistics, including minimum and maximum values, mean, median, and standard deviation, as well as the 5th and 95th percentiles. Percentiles are particularly useful statistical measures for describing data spread and identifying outliers. We use the value of the 5th percentile as the lowest threshold and the value of the 95th percentile as the highest threshold for extracting tree crowns.

We delineate tree crowns that exhibit spatial associations with road, and river segments. To do this, we generate five-meter buffers around these linear features and perform spatial selection. Additionally, using the spatial join technique, we calculate the number of tree crowns located within each segment of road, and river. We then isolate those segments with a higher density of tree crowns and assess their proximity to parks and forested areas.

3 Results

In the study area, the observed minimum and maximum height values for the collected sample crowns are 8.49 meters and 36.15 meters, respectively. The mean height is recorded at 22.03 meters, with the median slightly lower at 21.87 meters, accompanied by a standard deviation of 4.78 meters. To cover the majority of the data while excluding outliers, the 5th and 95th percentiles are computed, establishing a minimum threshold of 14.73 meters and a maximum of 29.37 meters. These thresholds identify approximately 159,000 objects, including but not limited to tree crowns. Through spatial selection, this number is reduced to 23,000 objects overlapping road and river buffers. Additionally, using spatial join, we identify the number of trees in each linear segment. The highest count is 180 trees within a single line segment. We reclassify the line segments as green corridors with a low, moderate, high, and very high probability based on the number of trees present in each segment. An example area with line segments of various green corridor probabilities is shown in Figure 1. Segments with more than 13 trees, constituting moderate to very high probability, are selected, and their proximity to roads, and rivers is calculated.

Of the 389 segments selected in the final step, 212 either directly adjoin or intersect with forests or parks. In contrast, 100 segments are located more than 100 meters from any forest or park. Furthermore, 54 segments are within a 50-meter radius, and 23 are less than 100 meters away from forests and parks.

4 Discussion and Conclusions

This case study aimed to identify green corridors, a type of UGSs often overlooked in green space mapping. Green corridors are characterized as linear structures that connect larger green spaces, thereby forming urban ecological networks. Our approach began with identifying trees distributed along linear structures such as roads and rivers, followed by extracting linear segments with a higher density of trees and assessing their proximity to larger green areas such as parks and forests.

To detect trees in the study area, we employ height thresholds, retrieved by an analysis of sample tree points and their height distribution. This method effectively identified a significant number of tree crowns. However, the total number of trees identified was considerably lower than the actual

Figure 1: Sample area covered by linear segments of various probabilities being green corridors.

tree coverage in Augsburg. We can explain this discrepancy by the timing of the DSM model’s acquisition in February, a period when deciduous trees, which predominantly constitute Augsburg’s green corridors, lack foliage. Consequently, the data set misses a substantial number of deciduous trees, leading to an underestimation of tree presence, particularly in streets with sparse tree coverage. Nonetheless, we are able to discern linear segments with a probability ranging from low to very high of being green corridors, a conclusion supported by their calculated proximity to forests and parks.

Currently, there is no dataset that includes information on green corridors. Creation and availability of such datasets are essential because they provide foundational data for numerous urban ecological studies. In line with the second principle of the rewilding guide suggested by Carver et al. (2021), core areas within a landscape are reservoirs of species diversity, and maintaining their interconnectedness is crucial for facilitating the movement of species across a more expansive landscape. Therefore, datasets on green corridors would be extremely useful in identifying where these linear connections exist within urban environments and in assessing the degree of connectivity between core areas. But since such data sets do not yet exist, our findings have not undergone statistical validation, although they have been confirmed through visual inspection. Consequently, the forthcoming steps will involve refining the results by tackling the limitations present in the datasets utilized. Particular emphasis will be placed on improving the quality of the OSM dataset, which presently exhibits low accuracy within the study region. Additionally, the exploration of more sophisticated deep learning approaches for extracting tree data from aerial images is required. This might, however, lead to a subsequent modification of our workflow to integrate new techniques.

5 Biography

Irada Ismayilova is a PhD student at the University of Augsburg, is keen in Urban Green Spaces, green space ontologies, and the identification of green spaces using knowledge-based, machine learning, and deep learning techniques. Sabine Timpf, a professor of geoinformatics at the University of Augsburg, focuses her research on exploring and analysing urban green spaces, spatial cognition in geospatial activities, as well as agent-based modeling and simulation.

References

- Carver, S., et al. (2021). Guiding principles for rewilding. *Conservation Biology*, 35(6), 1882–1893.
- Degerickx, J., Hermy, M., & Somers, B. (2020). Mapping functional urban green types using high resolution remote sensing data. *Sustainability*, 12(5), 2144.
- Forde, D., McElduff, L., & Rafferty, G. (2023). Alley greening: a tool for enhancing community resilience? *Local Environment*, (pp. 1–20).
- Heidt, V. & Neef, M. (2008). Benefits of urban green space for improving urban climate. In *Ecology, planning, and management of urban forests: International perspectives* (pp. 84–96). Springer.
- Lacasta, A. M., Peñaranda, A., & Cantalapiedra, I. R. (2018). Green streets for noise reduction. In *Nature Based Strategies for Urban and Building Sustainability* (pp. 181–190). Elsevier.
- Leichtle, T., Zehner, M., Kühnl, M., Martin, K., & Taubenböck, H. (2021). Urban trees—detection, delineation, quantification, and characterisation based on vhr remote sensing. *Proceedings of the real CORP, real CORP*, 7(10.09), 2021.
- Lin, W., et al. (2019). The effect of green space behaviour and per capita area in small urban green spaces on psychophysiological responses. *Landscape and Urban Planning*, 192, 103637.
- Peng, J., Zhao, H., & Liu, Y. (2017). Urban ecological corridors construction: A review. *Acta Ecologica Sinica*, 37(1), 23–30.
- Zhang, Z., Meerow, S., Newell, J. P., & Lindquist, M. (2019). Enhancing landscape connectivity through multifunctional green infrastructure corridor modeling and design. *Urban forestry & urban greening*, 38, 305–317.